

Common Regional Market

July 2024

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Common Regional Market, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Knowledge-intensive service exports” and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Source

Author’s calculations based on European Innovation Scoreboard 2022. EU countries and neighbouring countries database. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard_en#eis-interactive-tool (accessed 21 February 2024).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

	Prepared S3 and their implementation supported				Increased investment in SMEs		Linking Western Balkans education and innovation activities			
	S3 milestones	Local S3 Support	S3 dialogue	Peer exchange (events, docs)	Access to Finance (A2F) perception	Macro regional Strategies	Enterprise Europe Network and European Youth Event	WB in COST & EUREKA	IPR support	Infrastructure support
Albania	Not yet	Increased number of events	Numerous events with large number of participants	No new events reported	Moderate obstacle	Several programmes, joined Interreg Europe	Increased number of events, beneficiaries not specified	Increased participation and promotion of COST	No new events reported	New facility reported, no change in other sub-indicators
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Not yet	No new events reported	Information not provided	No new events reported	Moderate obstacle	Several programmes, joined Interreg Europe	Increased number of beneficiaries and events	No new events reported	Increased number of events, resources and participants	No new developments reported
Kosovo*	Not yet	Increased number of events	No new meeting reported	Increased number of events	Moderate obstacle	No new programmes joined	Increased number of beneficiaries and events	Increased participation in COST. No participation in EUREKA yet	Increased number of events and resources. Number of participants not provided	Increased number of facilities, increased budget allocation
Montenegro	In place	Increased number of events	Numerous events with large number of participants	Increased number of events and participants	Moderate obstacle	Several programmes, joined Interreg Europe	Increased number of beneficiaries and events. Not participating in EYE	No new results reported	Information not provided	Information not provided
North Macedonia	In place	Increased number of events and publications	Information not provided	Increased number of events	Moderate obstacle	Several programmes, joined Interreg Europe	Increased number of beneficiaries and events	Increased participation and promotion of COST & EUREKA	Increased number of events and resources. Number of participants not provided	No new developments reported
Serbia	In place	Increased number of events	No new meeting reported	Information not provided	Moderate obstacle	Several programmes, joined Interreg Europe	Increased number of beneficiaries and events	No new results reported	No new events reported	New facility reported, no change in other sub-indicators

Legend:

- On track or maintaining achievement
- Moderately improving, Challenges remain
- Stagnating, Significant challenges
- Decreasing, Major challenges
- Information not available

Highlights

Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia joining the Interreg Europe Programme

All Western Balkans economies participate in the Enterprise Europe Network

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